

Assessment of Stakeholder Perspectives on the Proposed Tourism Databank in Panglao, Bohol, Philippines

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Abstract

This study explores the implementation and assessment of the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD) as a digital solution to enhance local tourism governance in Panglao, Bohol. Using a descriptive mixed-method approach, data were collected through validated questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, documentation reviews, and observations from 101 respondents, including personnel in charge, accommodation establishments, and other tourism stakeholders. The findings revealed that while a majority of respondents were aware of general database systems (59.41%), only 61.39% were familiar with the current tourism database system used in the municipality. A significant 98.02% expressed willingness to adopt the PITD, citing improved data security, operational efficiency, and tourism development potential as key benefits. Thematic analysis of stakeholder responses emphasized the importance of system reliability and security, usability and accessibility, research integrity, and economic impact. Key features recommended for the PITD included user-friendly design, secure logins, and accessibility regardless of internet connectivity. The study also identified current system issues such as misreporting, delays in data processing, and paper-based redundancy. The proposed PITD aims to address these gaps by offering a centralized, reliable, and secure data management platform. Implications highlight the need for digital transformation, stakeholder training, and infrastructure improvement. The study concludes that a well-designed and inclusive tourism databank can significantly contribute to sustainable tourism development, efficient governance, and enhanced visitor satisfaction in Panglao. Recommendations include phased implementation, collaborative system design, and continuous improvement based on user feedback and evolving tourism trends.

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Introduction

Tourism plays a significant role in driving economic growth[1], especially in coastal destinations like Panglao, Bohol—one of the Philippines’ top tourist hotspots renowned for its white sandy beaches, world-class diving sites, and vibrant marine biodiversity[2]. The increasing influx of both domestic and foreign tourists, as evidenced by the significant rise in visitor arrivals from 302,952 in 2015 to over one million in 2019, has brought about complex social, environmental, and administrative challenges[3]. While the tourism industry fuels employment and local business growth—with nearly 10,000 job permits issued and nearly a thousand establishments operating—The same with the Island of Siargao[4], Panglao still lacks an efficient and centralized digital system to manage and monitor tourism-related data. Government offices such as the Panglao Municipal Tourism Office (PMTO), the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO), the Public Employment Services Office (PESO), and the Sangguniang Bayan of Panglao (SBP) currently operate without an integrated platform, resulting in fragmented reporting and inefficient information dissemination. This absence of a robust data management infrastructure hinders evidence-based policymaking and responsive service delivery in the tourism sector[5].

Despite Panglao’s growing prominence as a tourism destination, there remains a noticeable gap in digital governance tools that support sustainable tourism development[6]. Although several studies have highlighted the benefits of digitization in tourism management—such as improved transparency[7], better visitor experience[8], and efficient resource allocation[9]—few, if any, have focused on local-level implementation in second-tier cities or island municipalities like Panglao. Current literature is limited when it comes to practical applications of centralized tourism databanks in geographically isolated and tourism-dependent areas in the Philippines due to challenges in ineffective implementation of policies, decision-making, and work-life balance issues for tourism workers[10]. Moreover, most tourism monitoring systems are either paper-based or independently operated by individual stakeholders, resulting in duplication, inconsistent data, and difficulty in real-time coordination. There is a need for a systematic, localized solution that can unify data sources, streamline transactions, and generate accurate reports to guide

legislation, policy formulation, and investment decisions in tourism.

This study addresses the identified gap by proposing the development of the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD)—a centralized online database system that consolidates and manages tourism-related information within the Municipality of Panglao. The PITD is envisioned to serve as an accessible digital repository that integrates tourist records from the PMTO, employment and establishment data from PESO, and dive site utilization reports from MENRO. This innovation aims to enhance service efficiency, data security, and decision-making capacity through real-time data availability, minimized redundancy, and user-friendly online transactions. The study also explores user awareness and readiness for PITD adoption, assesses the limitations of the current manual system, and identifies the functional requirements for database design and testing. By providing a reliable, centralized digital platform, the PITD not only aims to improve the management of tourism activities but also serves as a strategic tool for community engagement, policy enhancement, and future research in sustainable local tourism development.

II. RELATED WORKS

Tourism continues to be a vital component of the global economy[11], with the sector's contribution to global GDP reaching US\$7.7 trillion in 2022, accounting for 7.6% of the global economy[12]. The resurgence of international tourism post-pandemic has underscored the importance of efficient information systems to manage the increasing influx of tourists[13]. In this context, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have become indispensable in enhancing the management and promotion of tourism destinations [14].

Recent advancements in big data analytics have significantly transformed tourism management. A study highlighted the development and execution of a Digital Tourism System (DTS) that utilizes big data to enhance decision-making processes in tourism management [15]. Such systems enable the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data, facilitating more informed and strategic decisions by tourism stakeholders.

The integration of real-time data insights has also proven beneficial [16]. For instance, a study by [17] Technology and ICT policies positively impact guest satisfaction in 4 and 5-star hotels in Nairobi City Country. This demonstrates the potential of real-time data systems in optimizing operational efficiency and enhancing the tourist experience.

Furthermore, the concept of smart tourism has gained traction, emphasizing the use of advanced technologies to create more interactive and personalized tourist experiences [18]. Digital tourism is advancing rapidly, leading to new scenarios, forms, and modes, and deep integration of digital economy and tourism real economy [19]. These initiatives often involve the use of mobile applications, IoT devices, and AI to provide tourists with real-time information and personalized recommendations [20].,

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques to explore the current status of tourism activity and the experiences of key stakeholders in Panglao, Bohol. This method allowed the researchers to describe the phenomenon in context while gathering in-depth insights from personnel of the Panglao Municipal Tourism Office (PMTO), Public Employment Services Office (PESO), Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO), and representatives of local tourism-related establishments.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Panglao, a premier tourist destination in Bohol. The research setting primarily included the Municipal Hall located in Poblacion, where relevant offices such as the PMTO, PESO, MENRO, and the Sangguniang Bayan are based. Panglao is well-known for its rich marine biodiversity and world-renowned beaches, making tourism a key economic driver.

Respondents and Sampling

A non-probability convenience sampling method was adopted to select 101 respondents comprising three groups: personnel-in-charge from government offices (PMTO, PESO, MENRO), accommodation establishments (hotels and resorts), and other tourism service providers such as restaurants and stores. This approach was selected for its cost-efficiency and accessibility, especially given the operational challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Table 1 below presents the distribution of respondents.

Table 1. Research Respondents

Group	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Accommodation Establishments (Hotels/Resorts)	55	54.45
Personnel-In-Charge (PMTO, PESO, MENRO, etc.)	24	23.76
Restaurants/Others (Not in Accommodations)	22	21.78
Total	101	100%

Research Instruments

To gather meaningful insights for the study, a combination of tools was used. The main instrument was a structured questionnaire carefully crafted by the researchers. It was pilot-tested and refined to make sure the questions were clear and consistent. To go beyond numbers and capture deeper perspectives, the study also used semi-structured interviews with key representatives from each group of respondents.

In addition to surveys and interviews, observational checklists, document reviews, and email exchanges helped provide supporting details and context. These tools worked together to give a well-rounded picture of how people view and respond to the proposed Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD).

The questionnaire itself was divided into five main sections: how aware respondents are of current and proposed tourism database systems; their willingness to adopt the PITD; their ideas for features and functions it should include; the benefits the respondents believe PITD could bring; and finally, space for

open feedback and suggestions. This approach made sure that both measurable data and personal insights were captured throughout the research..

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior approval to conduct the study was secured from the Office of the Mayor. Data collection followed ethical and procedural standards including informed consent, voluntary participation, and data privacy in compliance with Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Surveys were administered in person and online, supplemented by interviews and site observations.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, particularly frequency counts and percentage distribution, to summarize responses. Qualitative responses were thematically analyzed to enrich the interpretation of the quantitative findings and inform system design specifications.

Result and Discussion

All the respondents participated in the survey agree in giving their consent to participate in the study. The study collected responses from 101 participants, categorized based on gender, academic affiliation, age group, and family income. Below is a detailed breakdown of each demographic factor.

A. Awareness of Current Tourism Database System

Fig. 1. Awareness of the Current Tourism Database System Distribution

Fig.1 shows that out of the 101 individuals surveyed across key stakeholder groups in Panglao's tourism sector, a majority—62 respondents (61.39%)—indicated that the respondents were already aware of the existing or proposed tourism databank system. Among the personnel in charge from local government office

s, awareness was particularly high, with 18 out of 24 (75%) expressing familiarity with the system. This suggests strong engagement and communication within the implementing agencies. In contrast, accommodation establishments showed a lower awareness level, with only 30 out of 55 respondents (54.55%) indicating the respondents knew about the system, pointing to a need for improved outreach and orientation in this sector. The restaurant and other tourism-related service providers fell in between, with 14 out of 22 respondents (63.64%) reporting awareness. These figures highlight the importance of consistent and inclusive information dissemination across all stakeholder groups to ensure broad understanding and support for the PITD initiative.

Fig. 2. Awareness of a Database System

Fig. 2 shows that 59.41% of the total respondents were familiar with such systems. Interestingly, almost all personnel in charge (95.83%) indicated strong awareness, likely due to their exposure to data handling and digital record-keeping in government operations. On the other hand, only about half (52.73%) of the accommodation stakeholders and just over a third (36.36%) of the resto/others group expressed the same awareness. This gap underscores the importance of user education and digital literacy in successfully implementing a centralized tourism databank.

B. Willingness to Adopt the Tourism Database System

Fig. 3. Importance of Tourism Databank to Offices/Establishments

Fig. 3 shows that a strong willingness among stakeholders to adopt the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD), with 98.02% of respondents expressing support for its implementation. All personnel in charge and accommodation establishment representatives (100%) indicated readiness to integrate the PITD into their operations, recognizing its potential to enhance efficiency, streamline processes, and improve local tourism governance. While a small portion (9.09%) from the resto/others category expressed reservations, the overwhelming majority reflected a collective openness to digital transformation. This high level of acceptance across sectors highlights a favorable environment for the successful adoption and sustainability of the PITD in Panglao.

Fig. 4. Top Three Perceived Advantages of Tourism Databank

Fig. 4 shows that the respondents overwhelmingly prioritized improved data security, with 81 individuals selecting it as the most critical feature. This shows a strong concern for safeguarding sensitive tourism data.

ata. Reduced errors and increased data consistency followed closely, chosen by 74 respondents, reflecting the stakeholders' desire for accurate, reliable, and standardized information across offices and establishments. The third most favored advantage was greater data integrity and program independence, with 73 responses, highlighting the need for a system that not only ensures trustworthy data but also minimizes reliance on fragmented or manual processes. These insights emphasize the stakeholders' shared expectations for a secure, dependable, and autonomous tourism databank.

Fig. 5. Top Three preferred Database Design Qualities

Fig.5 shows that majority of respondents highlighted the importance of efficient access to data, with 83 respondents ranking it as the most essential feature. This reflects a strong preference for a system that allows quick and seamless retrieval of tourism-related information. The second most preferred quality was that the database should be clean, consistent, and easy to understand, chosen by 72 individuals. This indicates the stakeholders' desire for a user-friendly interface that ensures clarity and minimizes confusion. Lastly, support for the maintenance of data integrity ranked third, with 54 responses, showing that the system must ensure the reliability and accuracy of the stored data. These preferences underline the need for a well-structured and accessible database that is both efficient and dependable.

C. Expected Benefits of Tourism Databank

When evaluating the benefits of the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD) to the local tourism industr

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Fig. 6. Benefits to the Tourism Industry

the majority of respondents emphasized enhanced operational efficiency shown in Fig. 6, with 94 responses ranking it as the top benefit. This suggests that stakeholders believe the system will streamline processes and improve the overall functioning of tourism-related operations. Access to relevant and accurate information followed closely, with 86 responses, highlighting the importance of having up-to-date, reliable data to support decision-making and strategic planning. Lastly, the development of a new marketing environment was ranked third, with 85 responses, indicating that the PITD is seen as a tool to foster new opportunities for promoting Panglao’s tourism offerings. Together, these benefits point to a strong consensus that the PITD could significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the tourism industry in Panglao.

Fig. 7. Benefits to the Local Tourism Industry

Fig. 7 shows that the most frequently cited benefit was identifying tourism development opportunities, with

h 82 responses, suggesting that the system could play a key role in uncovering new areas for tourism growth and investment. Following closely, supporting the decision-making process ranked second with 78 responses, indicating that the PITD could be a valuable tool in guiding the municipality's planning and policy formulation. Finally, promoting sustainable tourism was ranked third with 75 responses, reflecting a shared view that the PITD could help ensure the long-term sustainability of tourism in the area by providing the necessary data for informed, responsible decisions. Together, these benefits show that the PITD is seen as a strategic asset for advancing tourism in Panglao while supporting its broader development goals.

Fig. 8. Benefits to the Tourist

The top benefit identified was satisfaction and repeat visits, along with the influence on other travelers, which received 85 responses shown in Fig. 8, suggesting that a well-managed tourism system can encourage return visits and positive word-of-mouth recommendations. Closely following, a healthy, clean, safe, and protected environment ranked second with 81 responses, reflecting the importance of maintaining high standards of safety and cleanliness to attract and retain visitors. Lastly, access to quality tourism services and products was ranked third with 80 responses, indicating that tourists highly value having reliable access to top-notch services during their stay. These benefits underline the pivotal role the PITD could play in enhancing the overall tourist experience in Panglao.

D. Issues encounter of the stakeholders in the Current Tourism System

1. *Inefficient Data Monitoring and Reporting* - Stakeholders from local government (PMTO, MENRO

- , and the Sangguniang Bayan) expressed concerns about the system's inability to accurately monitor tourist arrivals, services availed, and violations of tourism policies. Reports are often delayed, and many transactions remain undocumented, limiting the effectiveness of governance and planning.
2. *Compliance and Documentation Gaps*- PESO faces difficulty in tracking the employment and legal compliance of tourism-related establishments due to missing documentation (such as BIR, SSS, Philhealth, and Pagibig records) This results in a lack of transparency in actual workforce statistics.
 3. *Environmental Management Challenges* - MENRO noted the absence of a monitoring system for tourist numbers per site, making it hard to regulate environmental impact and generate reliable carrying capacity reports for protected marine areas and dive sites.
 4. *Redundancy and Inefficiency in Transactions* -Accommodation providers and other business report frequent duplication in paperwork and manual processing when interacting with different government offices. This not only causes delays but also leads to frustration among stakeholders.
 5. *Safety and Service Quality Concerns* -Tourists have experienced safety issues and occasional fraudulent practices. Instances of poor service quality from some tourism providers were also reported, threatening tourism reputation.
 6. *Bureaucratic Delays and Missed Opportunities* - Stakeholders described bureaucratic red tape as a barrier to growth, where delays in approval processes hinder tourism and hospitality-related investments and innovation.

E. Thematic Analysis of Respondents Responses

These responses and recommendations of the respondents are broken down into themes, codes, and sample responses from the three respondent groups (Personnel in Charge, Accommodation Establishments, and Resto/Others).

Table 2 shows that respondents' feedback highlights System Reliability and Security as a key concern. Participants emphasized the need for a secure system design, including secure login features and online a

ccessibility.

Table 2. System Reliability and Security

Theme	Code	Responses
System Reliability and Security	Secure System design	“Ensure the system is secure and accessible online” “Require secure log-in for tourism staff”
	Server/database availability	“Improve server and database reliability”
	Internet infrastructure	“Improve internet infrastructure” “Design for accessibility regardless of internet connectivity”

The responses also pointed out the importance of improving server and database reliability to ensure consistent system performance. Additionally, respondents stressed the need to enhance internet infrastructure and design the system to remain accessible even with limited connectivity, ensuring reliability across various user conditions.

Table 3. Usability and Accessibility

Theme	Code	Responses
Usability and Accessibility	User-friendly Interface, Low-cost	“The system must be user-friendly and cost-efficient”
	Inclusive participation	“Involve more establishments in data gathering”
	Low-cost, accessible tools	“Implement socially distanced technologies” “Design for accessibility regardless of internet connectivity”

Table 3 emphasized the importance of a user-friendly and cost-efficient interface, ensuring that the system is easy to use and affordable for stakeholders. There was also a call for inclusive participation, encouraging the involvement of more establishments in data gathering. Moreover, the feedback highlighted the need for accessible and low-cost technologies, including socially distanced tools and designs that remain functional even with limited internet connectivity, making the system more inclusive and adaptable.

Table 4. Research Integrity and Execution

Theme	Code	Responses
Research Integrity and Execution	Research preparedness	“Emphasize on-site preparation” “Maintain thorough documentation during your study”
	Passion and motivation	“Passion in research is essential” “I believe in your capability to deliver this system”
	Adoption of Best Practices	“Research best practices to strengthen PITD”

Table 4 stressed the value of research preparedness, recommending strong on-site preparation and comprehensive documentation to ensure credibility and accuracy. The respondents also emphasized the role of passion and motivation in driving meaningful results, expressing confidence in the research team's capabilities. Furthermore, the need to adopt best practices was underscored, encouraging the integration of proven methods to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD).

Table 5. System Enhancement and Improvement

Theme	Code	Responses
System Enhancement and Improvement	System upgrade suggestions	“Enhance the existing setup”
	Clean and Beautiful environment	“Promote cleanliness and beauty in Panglao”
	Environmentally responsive design	“Implement socially distanced technology”

Table 5 suggested the enhancement of the existing system setup to better meet operational demands. Additionally, there was a clear emphasis on maintaining a clean and beautiful environment, which aligns with the tourism identity of Panglao. Finally, calls for an environmentally responsive design—such as the implementation of socially distanced technologies—reflect the growing need for sustainable and health-conscious solutions in tourism system development.

Table 6. Economic and Developmental Impact

Theme	Code	Responses
	Economic opportunity creation	“Your research fosters economic opportunities and development”

Economic and Developmental Impact	Tourism development support	“PITD can help unlock future tourism growth”
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Table 6 acknowledged that the system could foster economic opportunities and development, particularly by empowering local businesses and stakeholders through data-driven decision-making. Additionally, there is strong belief that PITD can unlock future tourism growth, positioning it as a strategic tool in enhancing the competitiveness and sustainability of Panglao’s tourism industry.

Conclusion

This study explored the awareness, readiness, and perceived benefits of implementing the Panglao Island Tourism Databank (PITD) among key tourism stakeholders in Panglao, Bohol. The findings reveal that while a majority of respondents are aware of the current tourism database system, significant gaps remain in both functionality and stakeholder satisfaction. Notably, many establishments and offices experience challenges such as inefficient data tracking, redundancy in reporting, incomplete documentation, and weak infrastructure, which hinder effective tourism governance and service delivery.

The high level of willingness (98.02%) among respondents to adopt the PITD underscores a shared commitment to innovation and modernization of Panglao's tourism landscape. Stakeholders particularly emphasized the need for improved data security, accessibility, user-friendliness, and real-time data availability. Furthermore, suggested features—including secure login systems, clean interface design, and support for offline accessibility—reflect a strong preference for a responsive and resilient digital system. Thematic analysis also highlighted recurring concerns such as system reliability, inclusivity, economic impact, and environmental sustainability.

The PITD is seen not merely as a data repository but as a transformative tool for local development. It holds the potential to streamline tourism operations, enable evidence-based policy making, and support a clean, safe, and enjoyable environment for both locals and tourists. Importantly, the system is also envisioned as a platform for inter-agency coordination, marketing innovation, and sustainable tourism practices.

Recommendation

The findings have several recommendations for stakeholders, policymakers, and Government Officials aiming to intensify the tourism in Panglao:

1. Foster collaboration among stakeholders to ensure the PITD is relevant, practical, and inclusive.
2. Implement strong security protocols and data privacy measures to protect sensitive information.
3. Design the PITD to be user-friendly, low-cost, and accessible, even in areas with poor internet connectivity.
4. Upgrade local internet and server infrastructure to support seamless and reliable access to the system
5. Digitize government transactions to eliminate redundancy and enhance reporting and monitoring efficiency
6. Incorporate sustainable tourism tools that help manage visitor capacity and promote environmental responsibility.
7. Include economic analytics dashboards to support employment tracking and tourism development planning.
8. Integrate safety and satisfaction features for tourists, such as verified services and emergency access.
9. Document and share best practices for possible adoption by other tourism-focused municipalities.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

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